

Scopus[®]

Evaluation Report: SCOPUS.

Submitted to:

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Consultant|Strategic thinker|Customer Analyst|Employer

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ACCESS

Provider: Elsevier(An Information Analytics publishing company)
Headquarters: Amsterdam, Netherlands.

Parent company: RELX plc
Headquarters: London, England, UK.

Available languages: English, Japanese, Chinese(Traditional & Simplified)
and Russian.

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INTRODUCTION & BACKGROUND

- SCOPUS is a bibliographic database containing abstracts and citations for academic journal articles.
- SCOPUS is Elsevier's abstract and citation database **launched in November, 2004.**
- Available only through **online subscription.**
- Covers around 41,462 results.
- Subject fields: science, technology, medicine, social sciences, and arts and humanities.
- Incorporates patent database search.
- In 2016, citescore was introduced.

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FEATURES, PURPOSE AND DESIGN

FEATURES:

- Famous for its quality and standard indexed journals.
- Higher scientific quality compared to other popular indexation services as:
PubMed, EMBASE, EBSCO, MedLine, SCIRUS etc.
- Increases chances of citation
- Provides help in giving higher citation score.
- Improves visibility of the university.
- Data is updated periodically.
- Follows strict guidelines in terms of quality of journals and proceedings.
- Smart tools to track, analyze and visualize research.

PURPOSE:

- Giving continuous access to students, teachers, researchers and librarians to research output from around the world.
- Providing platform, tools, and insights to the people researching to connect to academia, government and corporations.
- With Elsevier as major solution provider, SCOPUS is well connected and grounded with community of researchers.

FORMAT and DESIGN:

Getting started: www.scopus.com. (Only Online format available)

SCOPUS Search API is based on Python SDK.

Can be used as registered or as an unregistered user.

Very easy to use.

Easy navigation.

Straight forward search bar.

Easy to use interface.

Author search available with use of ORCID(open digital identifier) Id.

Source search can be done using subject area, title, publish or ISSN.

TREATMENT:

SCOPUS gives four types of quality measures for each title, those are:

- a) H-index
- b) CiteScore
- c) SJR(SCImago journal rank)
- d) SNIP(Source Normalized Impact per paper)

SCOPUS indexes serial publications based on four source types which are as follows:

A) Journals(41,462 results):

- Makes up bulk of content.
- Can have various formats (print or electronic).
- Titles are according to content coverave policy.
- Any serial publication with an ISSN is suggested.

B) Book Series(1,561 results):

- Serial publication with series title, an ISSN or volume with ISBN.
- Each book has book title separate editor or editors.

C) Conference Proceedings(509 results): Enters SCOPUS in 2 different ways:

- Special issue of regular journal.
- Dedicated conference proceeding.

D) Trade Publications(803 results):

- Covers specific industry, trade or business.
- Magazine type of periodical on objects, new itirms and advertisements in the related field.

ARRANGEMENT:

- Open site www.scopus.com.
- In the search enter the query.
- Select search fields from drop-down list.
- For additional search, click '+' icon to enter additional search.
- Click 'Search'.
- The results page will show options to interact with.
- Click or browse through the documents to see the relevant topic.
- Analyse and sort:
 - Shown results are sorted by date
 - Most recent ones are shown first
 - To search different criteria, click 'Sort on'
 - Find the most cited documents.
 - Documents with unknown publication dates are taken as oldest.
 - Sorting applies to all the results
 - Sorting option remains selected for future.

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Overarching Findings

CRITERIA FOR SELECTION

Eligibility criteria for title to be considered for review:

- Should have peer reviewed content.
- Be published on regular basis.
- Have ISSN number with International ISSN centre.
- Have relevance,
- Easy to understand for an international audience.
- Use of publication ethics.
- Have publication malpractice statement.

SPECIAL FEATURES:

- a) Patents: Derived from five patent offices available in SCOPUS which are-
 - WIPO(World intellectual property organization)
 - EPO(European patent office)
 - USPTO(US patent office)
 - JPO(Japanese patent office)
 - UK intellectual property office(IPO.GOV.UK)
- b) Coverage of sources dating back to 1970.
- c) SCOPUS Article-in-Press(AiP) which helps accepted article be made available before official publication.
- d) Open Access journals: Peer reviewed journals registered as gold or subsidized OA under:
 - Directory of Open Access journals (<https://doaj.org>)
 - Directory of Open Access Scholarly resources(<https://road.issn.org>)
- e) Journal impact indicators available.
- f) Individual performance indicators available.

LIMITATIONS:

- a) Only analyses documents from 1996 to present.
- b) Not available in multilingual formats like other counterparts.
- c) SCOPUS policy doesnot include book reviews.

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Evaluation Conclusions

DRAWBACKS:

- a) Web of Science covers since the timespan of 1900s till present date giving it better citation tracking time.
- b) Google Scholar book reviews included as well.
- c) Google Scholar is not subscription based.

CONCLUSION:

SCOPUS is a good index parameter as it carries indexed journals of good reputation. Its master list contains thousands of good quality journals indexed. Has a content review board to keep journals not up to mark to be excluded. With every year evaluation it is important to see if a journal is delisted or is still included after time period of 1-2 years. Discontinuing journals after number of years can give uncertainty and disappointment among authors.

With new hybrid or combined discovery citation indexes it is now possible to use citation indexes for free using many free sources. Even with raw materials one should always put effort to combine, normalize and make the data clean before creating any kind of value added interface.

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References

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https://www.elsevier.com/solutions/scopus/how-scopus-works/content?dgcid=RN_AGCM_Sourced_300005030

<https://guides.lib.uw.edu/hsl/scopus/analytics>

<https://guides.lib.umich.edu/citation/Scopus>

<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11192-019-03264-z#author-information>

<https://www.relx.com/media/press-releases/archive/02-12-2009>

